

Antibody Characterization Report for SHIP1 (*INPP5D*)

YCharOS Antibody Characterization Report

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Target:

Short name: SHIP1

Recommended protein name: Phosphatidylinositol 3,4,5-trisphosphate 5-phosphatase 1

Alternative protein name: Inositol polyphosphate-5-phosphatase D, Inositol polyphosphate-5-phosphatase of 145 kDa, Phosphatidylinositol 4,5-bisphosphate 5-phosphatase, SH2 domain-containing inositol phosphatase 1, p150Ship

Gene name: *INPP5D*

Uniprot: Q92835

We are a third-party organization with the mission to characterize commercial antibodies for all human protein through open science [1]. In this study, we characterized 17 SHIP1 commercial antibodies for Western blot, and 15 antibodies for immunoprecipitation using a standardized experimental protocol [2] based on comparing read-outs in knockout (KO) cell lines and isogenic parental controls. SHIP1 protein levels was previously detected in myeloid cell lines and iPSC-derived microglia [3] were used in this study, as well as the U-937 cancer line. We identified many well-performing antibodies and encourage readers to use this report as a guide to select the most appropriate antibody for their specific needs.

The authors do not provide an assessment of the quality of the tested antibodies as their respective performances are limited to our finite experimental conditions. The readers should interpret the present findings based on their own scientific expertise. The authors acknowledge that an antibody that demonstrates specificity in the stated test conditions can be suboptimal in a different experimental format or in cell lines that differ from those directly tested here.

Table 1: Summary of the cell lines used

Institution	Catalog number	RRID (Cellosaurus)	Cell line	Genotype
Harvard Medical School/Brigham and Women's Hospital	-	-	iPSC-derived microglia	WT [3]
Harvard Medical School/Brigham and Women's Hospital	-	-	iPSC-derived microglia	<i>INPP5D</i> KO [3]
ATCC	CRL-1593.2	CVCL_0007	U-937	WT

Table 2: Summary of the SHIP1 antibodies tested

Company	Catalog number	Lot number	RRID (Antibody Registry)	Clonality	Clone ID	Host	Concentration (µg/µl)	Vendors recommended applications
Abcam	ab45142**	GR3222793-2	AB_11154124	recombinant-mono	EP378Y	rabbit	0.24	Wb,IP,IF
ABclonal	A0122	3521651004	AB_2769979	polyclonal	-	rabbit	1.87	Wb,IF
ABclonal	A3571**	400002047	AB_2863092	recombinant-mono	ARC2047	rabbit	0.79	Wb,IF
Aviva Systems Biology	ARP61033	QC31768-40750	AB_10880098	polyclonal	-	rabbit	0.50	Wb
Bio-Techne	AF10117	VEP0119011	AB_2940806	polyclonal	-	goat	0.20	Wb
Bio-Techne	MAB2317*	KXV0208121	AB_2233760	monoclonal	257812	rat	0.50	Wb,IF
Bio-Techne	NB110-81538*	539787	AB_1147000	monoclonal	SHIP-01	mouse	1.00	Wb
Cell Signaling Technology	2725**	1	AB_2126137	recombinant-mono	C15C9	rabbit	n/a	Wb,IP
Cell Signaling Technology	2727**	3	AB_2126136	recombinant-mono	C40G9	rabbit	n/a	Wb,IP
GeneTex	GTX01114**	822105924	AB_2888684	recombinant mono	SY11-08	rabbit	1.00	Wb
GeneTex	GTX03199**	822105920	AB_2940807	recombinant-mono	GT1287	rabbit	0.75	Wb
GeneTex	GTX79893*	822105973	AB_11170928	monoclonal	SHIP-02	mouse	1.00	Wb
Proteintech	19694-1-AP	49905	AB_10667407	polyclonal		rabbit	0.50	Wb,IP
Thermo Fisher Scientific	MA1-10449*	WE3266034	AB_11155187	monoclonal	SHIP-01	mouse	n/a	Wb,IF
Thermo Fisher Scientific	MA1-10450*	WE3266035	AB_11154124	monoclonal	SHIP-02	mouse	n/a	Wb,IF
Thermo Fisher Scientific	MA5-14893**	Wb3187253	AB_10977220	recombinant-mono	T.7.7	rabbit	n/a	Wb,IP,IF
Thermo Fisher Scientific	MA5-32049**	YJ4089243	AB_2809343	recombinant mono	SY11-08	rabbit	1.00	Wb

Wb=Western blot, IP= immunoprecipitation, IF=immunofluorescence, n/a=not available *=monoclonal antibody, **=recombinant antibody

Materials and methods

Antibodies

All the SHIP1 antibodies tested are listed in Table 2. Peroxidase-conjugated goat anti-rabbit, anti-rat, and anti-mouse antibodies are from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number 65-6120, 31470, and 62-6520, respectively). Peroxidase-conjugated donkey anti-goat is from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number A15999).

CRISPR/Cas9 genome editing

Cell lines used are listed in Table 1. *INPP5D* KO iPSC-derived microglia were generated as described previously [3].

Cell culture

iPSC-derived microglia were generated from human iPSCs using a previously published protocol [3]. Briefly, iPSCs were maintained in StemFlex media (ThermoFisher Scientific) and differentiated into HPCs using the StemDiff Hematopoietic Kit (StemCell Technologies). Cells were replated onto 6 well plates at day 12 of differentiation, after which they were fed with iMG media: DMEM/F12, 2x insulin-transferrin-selenite, 1x B27, 0.5x N2, 1x glutamax, 1x non-essential amino acids, 400 μ M monothioglycerol, 5 μ g/mL insulin. iMG media was supplemented with fresh cytokines before each use: 100 ng/mL IL-34 (Peprotech), 50ng/mL TGF β 1 (Millitenyi Biotech), and 25 ng/mL M-CSF (ThermoFisher Scientific). Cells were supplemented with 1 mL of fresh iMG media and cytokines on days 14, 16 and 18. On day 20, cells were dissociated with PBS and replated onto 24 well plates at 100,000 cells/well. 0.5 mL of fresh iMG media and the three cytokines were added to each well on day 22, and 0.5 mL of media was replaced every other day until day 37. Starting at day 37, the iMG media was supplemented with two additional cytokines: 100ng/mL CD200 (Novoprotein) and 100ng/mL CX3CL1 (Peprotech) every other day until harvest at day 40. U-937 cells were cultured in RPMI 1640 (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Gibco cat. number A1049101) containing 10% fetal bovine serum (Wisent, cat. number 080450), 2 mM L-glutamate (Wisent cat. number 609065, 100 IU penicillin and 100 μ g/ml streptomycin (Wisent cat. number 450201). Cells were treated with 200 ng/ml of PMA (Phorbol 12-myristate 13-acetate) from Abcam (cat. number ab147465) for 2 consecutive nights. PMA was diluted in fresh complete medium before both treatments.

Antibody screening by Western blot

Western blots were performed as described in our standard operating procedure [4]. WT and *INPP5D* KO iPSC-derived microglia (listed in Table 1) were collected in RIPA buffer (25mM Tris-HCl pH 7.6, 150mM NaCl, 1% NP-40, 1% sodium deoxycholate, 0.1% SDS) from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number 89901) supplemented with cOmplete protease inhibitor cocktail (Roche) and PhoSTOP phosphatase inhibitor (Roche). Lysates were incubated for 30 min on ice. Lysates were spun at ~15,000xg for 10 min at 4°C and equal protein aliquots of the supernatants were analyzed by SDS-PAGE and Western blot. BLUelf prestained protein ladder from GeneDireX (cat. number PM008-0500) was used.

Western blots were performed with precast midi 4-20% Tris-Glycine polyacrylamide gels from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number WXP42012BOX) ran with Tris/Glycine/SDS buffer from Bio-Rad (cat. number 1610772), loaded in Laemmli loading sample buffer from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number AAJ61337AD) and transferred on nitrocellulose membranes. Proteins on the blots were visualized with Ponceau S staining (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number BP103-10) which is scanned to show together with individual Western blot. Blots were blocked with 5% milk for 1 hr, and antibodies were incubated O/N at 4°C with 5% milk in TBS with 0,1% Tween 20 (TBST) from Cell Signaling (cat. number 9997). Following three washes with TBST, the peroxidase conjugated secondary antibody was incubated at a dilution of ~0.2 µg/ml in TBST with 5% milk for 1 hr at room temperature followed by three washes with TBST. Membranes were incubated with Pierce ECL from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number 32106) prior to detection with the iBright™ CL1500 Imaging System from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number A44240).

Antibody screening by immunoprecipitation

Immunoprecipitation was performed as described in our standard operating procedure [5]. Antibody-beads conjugates were prepared by adding 2 µg of antibody (or 10 µl of antibodies 2725**, 2727**, MA5-10449*, MA5-10450*, and MA5-14893**) to 500 µl of Pierce IP Lysis Buffer from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number 87788) in a microcentrifuge tube, together with 30µl of Dynabeads protein A- (for rabbit antibodies) or protein G- (for mouse, goat, and rat antibodies) from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number 10002D and 10004D, respectively). Tubes were rocked for ~1 hr at 4°C followed by two washes to remove unbound antibodies.

U-937 WT treated with PMA were collected in Pierce IP buffer (25 mM Tris-HCl pH 7.4, 150 mM NaCl, 1 mM EDTA, 1% NP-40 and 5% glycerol) supplemented with protease inhibitor. Lysates were rocked 30 min at 4°C and spun at 110,000xg for 15 min at 4°C. 0.5 ml aliquots at 2.0 mg/ml of lysate were incubated with an antibody-bead conjugate for ~1 hr at 4°C. The unbound fractions were collected, and beads were subsequently washed three times with 1.0 ml of IP lysis buffer

and processed for SDS-PAGE and Western blot on precast midi 4-20% Tris-Glycine polyacrylamide gels. Anti-mouse IgG for IP:HRP (Abcam, cat. number ab131368) was used as a secondary detection system at a concentration of 0.3 µg/ml.

Figure 1: SHIP1 antibody screening by Western blot

Figure 2: SHIP1 antibody screening by immunoprecipitation (1/2)

Figure 2: SHIP1 antibody screening by immunoprecipitation (2/2)

Figure 1: SHIP1 antibody screening by Western blot.

A) Lysates of WT and *INPP5D* KO iPSC-derived microglia were prepared, and 10 µg of protein were processed for Western blot with the indicated SHIP1 antibodies. The Ponceau stained transfers of each blot are shown. Antibody dilution used: ab45142** at 1/1000, A0122 at 1/500, A3571** at 1/500, ARP61033 at 1/500, AF10117 at 1/200, MAB2317* at 1/100, NB110-81538* at 1/1000, 2725** at 1/500, 2727** at 1/500, GTX01114** at 1/500, GTX03199** at 1/500, GTX79893* at 1/500, 19694-1-AP at 1/500, MA1-10449* at 1/1000, MA1-10450* at 1/1000, MA5-14893** at 1/1000, MA5-32049** at 1/1000. **B)** SHIP1 expression was confirmed in U-937 using Western blot. U-937 were treated or not using PMA as described in the methods section. Lysates were prepared as in A). MA1-10449* was used at 1/1000. Predicted band size: 133 kDa. *=monoclonal antibody, **=recombinant antibody

Figure 2: SHIP1 antibody screening by immunoprecipitation.

PMA-treated U-937 lysates were prepared in IP buffer, and immunoprecipitation was performed using 2.0 µg of the indicated SHIP1 antibodies pre-coupled to Dynabeads protein A or protein G. Samples were washed and processed for Western blot with the indicated SHIP1 antibody. For Western blot, MA1-10449* and MA1-10450* were used at 1/500. The Ponceau stained transfers of each blot are shown. SM=4% starting material; UB=4% unbound fraction; IP=immunoprecipitate. *=monoclonal antibody, **=recombinant antibody

References

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